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New Ideas On Super Decompenation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique-Decompositions In Cancer's Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph

Henry Garrett · Independent Researcher · Department of Mathematics ·
DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com · Manhattan, NY, USA

1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Clique-Decompositions pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. ((Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive

Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; an Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions
SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme
coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the
Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they
form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is
corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains
the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum
Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is
corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme
V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S
of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive
Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; a Neutrosophic
V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; an Extreme V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions 90
 SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic 91
 e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic 92
 re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic 93
 v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic 94
 rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph 95
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme 96
 coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the 97
 Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme 98
 cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices 99
 such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Extreme 100
 power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic 101
 SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic 102
 e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic 103
 re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic 104
 v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic 105
 rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic 106
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains 107
 the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum 108
 Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic 109
 SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic 110
 SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 111
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is 112
 corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is 113
 introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions 114
 and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Two different types of 115
 SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the 116
 SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are 117
 well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of 118
 this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the 119
 comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and 120
 fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the 121
 examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The 122
 applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing 123
 research. The "Cancer's Recognition" are the under research to figure out the 124
 challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. 125
 The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of 126
 them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These 127
 types are all officially called "SuperHyperVertex" but the relations amid them all 128
 officially called "SuperHyperEdge". The frameworks "SuperHyperGraph" and 129
 "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" are chosen and elected to research about "Cancer's 130
 Recognition". Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues 131
 to research on theoretical segments and "Cancer's Recognition". Some avenues are 132
 posed to pursue this research. It's also officially collected in the form of some questions 133
 and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then 134
 δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a 135
 maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the 136
 (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are 137
 $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first 138
 Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds 139
 if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic 140
 δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is a maximal Neutrosophic of 141
 SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the 142

following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It's redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, "The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" with the key points, "The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet", "The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints". To get structural examples and instances, I'm going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperClique-Decompositions until the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.] SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as

follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multiple separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions or the strongest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, called SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and the strongest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperClique-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Cancer's Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognition" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances' styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called "SuperHyperClique-Decompositions" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Extreme SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions or the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in those Extreme SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Extreme SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a

SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any
SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “amount of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It's motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” and “Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Extreme SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what's going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, are figured out in sections “SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” and “Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Clique-Decompositions to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Extreme SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what's done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “SuperHyperClique-Decompositions”, “Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what's done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “SuperHyperClique-Decompositions”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what's done and what's

happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Extreme Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [120]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [120]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Clique-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $] -0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Clique-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\begin{aligned} T_A(X) &= \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ I_A(X) &= \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ \text{and } F_A(X) &= \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 400
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 401
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 402
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 404
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 406
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If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 408
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Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3). 410

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 411
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- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 413
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 414
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 415
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 416

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 417

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 418
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- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 420
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 421
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- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 423
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- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 425
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- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 427
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 428

$$(vii) \sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(viii) \sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V, (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n').$$

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;

- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 471
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- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 474
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- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. 477
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Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold: 480
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- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 483
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 484
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 485
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 486
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 487
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 488
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 489
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 490
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 491
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Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 493

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 494

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 495
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 496
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 497
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 498
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Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [120], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [120], Definition 5.4, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a, E'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a, V'_b \text{ are Clique};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme

SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

(v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;

(vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;

(vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

(i) an δ -**SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)| &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)| &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

(ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath , SuperHyperClique-Decompositions,

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique-Decompositions** if the Table (3) holds.

4 Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Extreme event).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Any Extreme k -subset of A of V is called **Extreme k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Extreme subset of A of V is called **Extreme event**. The following expression is called **Extreme probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Extreme Independent).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. s Extreme k -events A_i , $i \in I$ is called **Extreme s -independent** if the following expression is called **Extreme s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Extreme k -events of A and B is called **Extreme independent**. The following expression is called **Extreme independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Extreme Variable).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Any k -function Clique-Decompositions like E is called **Extreme k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Clique-Decompositions like E is called **Extreme Variable**.

The notion of independent on Extreme Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Extreme Expectation).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Expectation** if the following expression is called **Extreme Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Extreme Crossing).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A Extreme number is called **Extreme Crossing** if the following expression is called **Extreme Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let m and n propose special Clique-Decompositions. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Extreme random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Extreme independently with probability Clique-Decompositions $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Extreme number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Extreme

number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Zcr(H)Y - 3X$. By linearity of Extreme Expectation,

$$E(Z)E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pm$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G)p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

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Theorem 4.7. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Extreme number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

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Proof. Form a Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between consecutive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Extreme SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Extreme crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. $\square$

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Theorem 4.8. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Extreme number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Extreme SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between consecutive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

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$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G)k - n$. Now $cr(G)n(n-1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n-1)cr(G)(k-n)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. $\square$

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Proposition 4.9. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X be a nonnegative Extreme Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Clique-Decompositions (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k + 1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Extreme Variable for this Extreme Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k + 1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1 - p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p \binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k2p^{-1} \log n$, so $ne^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Extreme SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Extreme Variance).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. A Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Variance** if the following expression is called **Extreme Variance criteria**

$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X be a Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X be a Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let X_n be a Extreme Variable in a probability Clique-Decompositions (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then

$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. $\square$

Theorem 4.15. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$.

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. $\square$

Corollary 4.16. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

- (i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* . 818

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 819 820

Definition 4.17. (Extreme Threshold). 821

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let P be a monotone property of SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a **Extreme Threshold** for P is a function $f(n)$ such that: 822 823 824 825

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P , 826

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P . 827

Definition 4.18. (Extreme Balanced). 828

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let F be a fixed Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a copy of F as a Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Extreme Balanced**. 829 830 831 832

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. Let F be a nonempty balanced Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F as a Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph. 833 834 835 836 837

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Clique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 838 839

Example 4.20. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 840 841

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 842 843 844 845 846 847 848 849 850

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} = \{\{E_4\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_1\}, \{V_2\}, \{V_3\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_4\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . 851 852 853 854 855 856

Figure 1. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_4\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_1\}, \{V_2\}, \{V_3\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_4\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_4\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_1\}, \{V_2\}, \{V_3\}, \{V_1, V_2\}, \{V_1, V_4\}, \{V_2, V_4\}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

Figure 2. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_4\}, \{E_5\}, \{E_1, E_4\}, \{E_1, E_5\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_2, V_3, N, F, V_4\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3, N, F, H\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3, N, F, O\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3z^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}_{i \neq j}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{Four Choose Two})z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=1}^5, \{V_i\}_{i=5}^8, \dots\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^5 + 2z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 5. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_1, E_2\}, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = az^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{V_1, V_2\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = bz. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} = \\ \{\{E_i, E_{13}, E_{14}, E_{16}\}_{i=3}^7, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 2z^8 + z^7. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} = \\ \{\{V_i, V_{13}\}_{i=4}^7, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 2z^5 + z^4. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 6. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 7. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 882
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4 & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{\{V_{13}, V_i\}_{i=4}^7, \{V_{14}, V_i\}_{i=8}^{11}, \{V_{12}, V_i\}_{i=1}^3, \{V_i\}_{i=12}^{14}\} & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5 + z^4 + z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 885
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{\{E_i, E_{i+1}\}_{i=1}^{10}\} & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
 \{\{V_i, V_{i+1}\}_{i=1}^{10}, \{V_i, V_{22}\}_{i=11}^{20}\} & \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + z^{11}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 9. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 890
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} = \{E_1, E_4, E_5, E_6, \{E_4, E_5, E_6\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z^1 + z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{\{V_{13}, V_i\}_{i=4}^7, \{V_{14}, V_i\}_{i=8}^{11}, \{V_{12}, V_i\}_{i=1}^3, \{V_i\}_{i=12}^{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^5 + z^4 + z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 893
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} = \{\{E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_2, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4 + z^3 + az^2 + 7z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{\{V_4, V_5, V_6\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^3 + az^2 + 6z.$$

Figure 10. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 897
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{E_1, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + 6z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_7, V_8\}, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5 + az^2 + 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 901
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ &= \{\{E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_2, E_4, E_5\}, \{E_1, E_9, E_{10}\}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4 + 2z^3 + az^2 + 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_4, V_5, V_6\}, \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^3 + az^2 + 6z. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 11. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 13. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 906
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2 + 3z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 909
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2 + 5z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2 + 6z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 913
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Figure 14. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 16. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 4z^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{17}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^{10} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 4z^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{17}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^{10} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 17. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{17}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{10} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + 12z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_8}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^9 + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 18. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 20. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 930
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^2 + 10z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_6}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= az^b + \dots + kz. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 933
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2 + 2z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_2}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{10} + \dots + 10z. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 21. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^3 + az^2 + 5z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ = \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_3}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^{12} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Figure 22. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Clique-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions.

Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Extreme number of type-result-R-Clique-Decompositions has, the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality, is the Extreme cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Extreme type-result-R-Clique-Decompositions with the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for cardinality.

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

Is a Extreme type-result-Clique-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Extreme type-result-Clique-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions since neither amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

This Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Extreme cardinality indicates that these Extreme type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Extreme lower bound in the term of Extreme sharpness. In other words, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

Is a quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Extreme SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Extreme structure of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions decorates the Extreme SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Extreme connections so as this Extreme style implies different versions of Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Extreme cardinality in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Extreme bound is to have the maximum Extreme groups of Extreme SuperHyperVertices have perfect Extreme connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Extreme SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Extreme SuperHyperGraph arising from its Extreme properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Extreme SuperHyperSet, then there's no Extreme connection. Furthermore, the Extreme existence of one Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no Extreme effect to talk about the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Since at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Extreme background of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The Extreme SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Extreme SuperHyperEdge but at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices make the Extreme version of Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Extreme setting of non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Extreme adjective for the initial Extreme SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Extreme appearance of the loop Extreme version of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge and this Extreme SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Extreme adjective "loop" on the basic Extreme framework engages one Extreme SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Extreme setting. With these Extreme bases, on a Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions has the Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions has the Extreme cardinality at least a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Extreme SuperHyperSet isn't a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions since either the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Extreme usage of this Extreme framework and even more there's no Extreme connection inside or the Extreme SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Extreme contradiction with the term "Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions" since the maximum Extreme cardinality never happens for

this Extreme style of the Extreme SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Extreme connection inside as mentioned in first Extreme case in the forms of drawback for this selected Extreme SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Comes up. This Extreme case implies having the Extreme style of on-quasi-triangle Extreme style on the every Extreme elements of this Extreme SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that some Extreme amount of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Extreme style. The Extreme cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

But the lower Extreme bound is up. Thus the minimum Extreme cardinality of the maximum Extreme cardinality ends up the Extreme discussion. The first Extreme term refers to the Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Extreme SuperHyperClass of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Extreme style amid some amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices. This Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperModel proposes a Extreme SuperHyperSet has only some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices from one Extreme SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Extreme amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The Extreme cardinality of this Extreme SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Extreme case is occurred in the minimum Extreme situation. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Extreme cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Contains some Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Extreme SuperHyperEdges for amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices taken from the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

It means that the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Is a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph as used Extreme background in the Extreme terms of worst Extreme case and the common theme of the lower Extreme bound occurred in the specific Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are Extreme free-quasi-triangle.

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}$ has z Extreme number of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Then every Extreme SuperHyperVertex has at least no

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Extreme SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Extreme SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Those Extreme SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Extreme style-R-Clique-Decompositions. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Extreme SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions but with slightly differences in the maximum Extreme cardinality amid those Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}_{\text{Extreme cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Let $Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

But with the slightly differences,

Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \overset{E_x}{\sim} Z_j, \}.$$

Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Extreme intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Extreme Clique-Decompositions, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$

could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Clique-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Extreme SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Extreme optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices but this Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions where the Extreme completion of the Extreme incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literally, a Extreme embedded R-Clique-Decompositions. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality and they're Extreme SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Extreme style of the embedded Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. The interior types of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Extreme number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Extreme SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices pose the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Thus Extreme exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and in Extreme SuperHyperRelation with the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices in that Extreme SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Extreme Clique-Decompositions, there's the usage of exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. The Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions with the inclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, is a Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Extreme

SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions has two titles. a Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions and its corresponded quasi-maximum Extreme R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Extreme number, there's a Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions with that quasi-maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph, then the Extreme quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositionss for all Extreme numbers less than its Extreme corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositionss acted on the all possible used formations of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Extreme number. This Extreme number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Clique-Decompositionss. Let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}$ be a Extreme number, a Extreme SuperHyperSet and a Extreme Clique-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Extreme Clique-Decompositions.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Extreme Clique-Decompositions poses the upcoming expressions. 1062
1063

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1064

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

And then, 1065

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook. 1066

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}, \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It’s, literarily, another name for “Extreme Quasi-Clique-Decompositions” but, precisely, it’s the generalization of “Extreme Quasi-Clique-Decompositions” since “Extreme Quasi-Clique-Decompositions” happens “Extreme Clique-Decompositions” in a Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Extreme Clique-Decompositions” in a Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Extreme SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Extreme Quasi-Clique-Decompositions”, and “Extreme Clique-Decompositions” are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}}$ be a Extreme number, a Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Extreme Clique-Decompositions and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge amid some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Extreme Clique-Decompositions** is related to the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There's not only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Clique-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Clique-Decompositions is a Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn't have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet since they've come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Clique-Decompositions **and** it's an Extreme **Clique-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some amount

Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Clique-Decompositions. There isn't only less than two Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Extreme free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Extreme on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Extreme stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions amid those obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Clique-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Extreme SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Extreme numbers of those Extreme SuperHyperVertices from that Extreme SuperHyperEdge excluding more than r distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Since it doesn't have **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions. Since it **doesn't do** the Extreme procedure such that such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Extreme SuperHyperVertex, titled its Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the Extreme SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Extreme procedure"]. There's only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Extreme SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Extreme SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Extreme pairs are titled Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Extreme R-Clique-Decompositions only contains all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices from the unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Clique-Decompositions, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions. The Extreme

SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)| \text{Extreme Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)| \text{Extreme Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions. The
Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)| \text{Extreme Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)| \text{Extreme Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an **Extreme Clique-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with
the maximum Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme
SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex
of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for
all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices
inside the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme
Clique-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called
the Extreme Clique-Decompositions is a Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two**
Extreme SuperHyperVertices. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme
SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)| \text{Extreme Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)| \text{Extreme Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme
SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the
Extreme Clique-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of

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the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Clique-Decompositions. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Extreme Clique-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Clique-Decompositions **and** it's an Extreme **Clique-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme Clique-Decompositions,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme
Clique-Decompositions, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious
simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

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“Extreme Clique-Decompositions”

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amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

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Extreme Clique-Decompositions,

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is only and only

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Clique-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

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5 The Extreme Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

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The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme
SuperHyperClasses.

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Proposition 5.1. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 1207

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= (|E_{NSHG}| - 1)z^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1208

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. 1210

There's a new way to redefine as 1211

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1212
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1213
The latter is straightforward. □ 1214

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath 1215
 $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the 1216
Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1217

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. 1218
Then 1219

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= (|E_{NSHG}|)z^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 23. a Extreme SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Example (16.5)

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{\lfloor \frac{|ENSHG|}{3} \rfloor}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\lfloor \frac{|ENSHG|}{3} \rfloor}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\lfloor \frac{|ENSHG|}{3} \rfloor}, V_{\lfloor \frac{|ENSHG|}{3} \rfloor}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in

Figure 24. a Extreme SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.7)

the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1229

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Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then 1231

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1232

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & \text{CENTER}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, \text{CENTER}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 1234

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. a Extreme SuperHyperStar Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.9)

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{E_1, E_2\}_{i=1}^{|P_{NSHG}^{\max}|}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P_i \in \{P_a \mid |P_a| = \max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}\}}, \{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_i, V_k\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}} + z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in ENSHG} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in ENSHG} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in ENSHG} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in ENSHG} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.8. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Figure 26. Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Example (16.11)

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E). Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{E_1, E_2\}_{i=1}^{|P_{NSHG}^{\max}|}, \{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in P_i \in \{P_a \mid |P_a| = \max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}\}}, \{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \{V_i, V_j\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\max |P_b|_{P_b \in P_{NSHG}}} + z^{\max |E_b|_{E_b \in E_{NSHG}}} + \dots + az.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1269

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

1270

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i| = \min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{E_i, E_j\}, \{E_k\}\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^2 + (|E_{NSHG}|)z. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-Clique-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in E_i^* \in \{E_a^* \mid |E_a^*| = \max |E_b^*|_{E_b^* \in E_{NSHG}^*}\}}, \{V_i\}_{V_i \in E_c}, \dots, \{V_i, V_j\}, \dots\} \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-Clique-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\max |E_b^*|_{E_b^* \in E_{NSHG}^*}} + z^{\max |E_b^*|_{E_b^* \in E_{NSHG}^*}} + \dots + az. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^* \end{aligned}$$

Figure 27. a Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Example (16.13)

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperClique-Decompositions proposes some longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.12. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, and the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, some general results are

Figure 28. a Extreme SuperHyperWheel Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions in the Extreme Example (16.15)

introduced. 1314

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets. 1315
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Corollary 6.2. Assume Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then 1317

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Extreme SuperHyperClique – Decompositions} = \\ & \{ \text{the SuperHyperClique – Decompositions of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \\ & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \text{SuperHyperClique – Decompositions} \\ & | \text{ExtremecardinalityamidthoseSuperHyperClique – Decompositions.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively. 1318
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Corollary 6.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and SuperHyperClique-Decompositions coincide. 1321
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Corollary 6.4. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if and only if it’s a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1324
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Corollary 6.5. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions if and only if it’s a longest SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1327
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Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and reversely. 1331
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1333

Corollary 6.7. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions is its SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and reversely. 1334
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Corollary 6.8. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* isn't well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* isn't well-defined. 1339
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Corollary 6.9. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* isn't well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* isn't well-defined. 1342
1343
1344

Corollary 6.10. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel)*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* isn't well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* isn't well-defined. 1345
1346
1347
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Corollary 6.11. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* is well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* is well-defined. 1350
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Corollary 6.12. Assume *SuperHyperClasses* of a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* is well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* is well-defined. 1353
1354
1355

Corollary 6.13. Assume a *Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel)*. Then its *Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* is well-defined if and only if its *SuperHyperClique-Decompositions* is well-defined. 1356
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then V is 1361
(i) : the dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1362
(ii) : the strong dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1363
(iii) : the connected dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1364
(iv) : the δ -dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1365
(v) : the strong δ -dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1366
(vi) : the connected δ -dual *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*. 1367

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then $\emptyset$ is 1368
(i) : the *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1369
(ii) : the strong *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1370
(iii) : the connected *defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1371
(iv) : the δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1372
(v) : the strong δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1373
(vi) : the connected δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*. 1374

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a *Extreme SuperHyperGraph*. Then an *independent SuperHyperSet* is 1375
1376
(i) : the *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions*; 1377

- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1378
- (iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1379
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1380
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1381
- (vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1382

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1383
1384
1385

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1386
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1387
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1388
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1389
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1390
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1391

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1392

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1393
1394

- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1395
- (ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1396
- (iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1397
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1398
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1399
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1400
1401

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1402

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperClique-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1403
1404
1405

- (i) : the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1406
- (ii) : the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1407
- (iii) : the connected SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1408
- (iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1409
- (v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1410
- (vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1411

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1412
1413

Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1414
1415

(i) : the dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1416

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1417

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1418

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1419

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1420

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1421

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1422
1423

Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1424
1425
1426
1427
1428

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1429

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1430

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1431

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1432

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1433

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1434
1435

Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1436
1437
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1439
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1441

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1442

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1443

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1444

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1445

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1446

(vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1447

Proposition 6.23. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of

- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1448
- (ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1449
- (iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1450
- (iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1451
- (v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1452
- (vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1453

is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1454

Proposition 6.24. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1455
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1456
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1457
- (iv) : SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1458
- (v) : strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1459
- (vi) : connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1460

Proposition 6.25. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Extreme number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$. 1461

Proposition 6.26. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \sum_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} \subseteq V} \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1462
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1463
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1464
- (iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1465
- (v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1466
- (vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1467

Proposition 6.27. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$.
The number is 0 and the Extreme number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iv) : 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (v) : strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (vi) : connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 6.28. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.

Proposition 6.29. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperClique-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Extreme number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 6.30. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;
- (vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 6.31. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs.

Proposition 6.32. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then
 $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$;

(ii) $vx \in E$.

Proposition 6.33. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then

(i) S is SuperHyperClique-Decompositions set;

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number.

Proposition 6.34. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$;

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$.

Proposition 6.35. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$;

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$.

Proposition 6.36. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$;

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 6.37. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$;

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S=\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S=\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\};$ 1560
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1561
1562

Proposition 6.39. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. Then* 1563
1564

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1565
1566
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ *and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\};$* 1567
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S=\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S=\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1568
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1569
1570

Proposition 6.40. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be SuperHyperStar. Then* 1571

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1572
- (ii) $\Gamma = 1;$ 1573
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c);$ 1574
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1575
1576

Proposition 6.41. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be SuperHyperWheel. Then* 1577

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1578
1579
- (ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|;$ 1580
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s);$ 1581
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1582
1583

Proposition 6.42. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then* 1584

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1585
1586
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1;$ 1587
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}};$ 1588
- (iv) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.* 1589
1590

Proposition 6.43. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then* 1591

- (i) *the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions;* 1592
1593
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor;$ 1594

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1595

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1596
1597

Proposition 6.44. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Extreme SuperHyperStars with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1598
1599

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1600
1601

(ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1602

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1603

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1604
1605

Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1606
1607
1608

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1609
1610

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1611

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1612

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1613
1614

Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1615
1616
1617

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1618
1619

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1620

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1621

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperClique-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1622
1623

Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1624
1625

(i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1626
1627
1628

(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1629
1630
1631

Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1632
1633

- (i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1634
1635
1636
- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1637
1638
1639

Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1640
1641
1642

- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1643
1644
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1645
1646
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1647
1648
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1649
1650

Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1651
1652
1653

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1654
1655
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1656
1657
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1658
1659
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1660
1661

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1662
1663
1664

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1665
1666
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1667
1668
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions; 1669
1670
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. 1671
1672

Proposition 6.52. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph$ which is a $SuperHyperComplete$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$.*

Proposition 6.53. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph$ which is $SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (ii) *$\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (iii) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (iv) *$\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$.*

Proposition 6.54. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph$ which is $SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperClique-Decompositions$.*

7 Extreme Applications in Cancer's Extreme Recognition

The cancer is the Extreme disease but the Extreme model is going to figure out what's going on this Extreme phenomenon. The special Extreme case of this Extreme disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Extreme recognition of the cancer could help to find some Extreme treatments for this Extreme disease.

In the following, some Extreme steps are Extreme devised on this disease.

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. a Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions

The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous
 Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (29), is
 the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

9 Case 2: The Increasing Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (30), the Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
 By using the Extreme Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained.
 The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous
 result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (30),
 is the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions.

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?

Question 10.2. Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions?

Question 10.3. Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?

Question 10.4. Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions?

Problem 10.5. The SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, are there else?

Problem 10.6. Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?

Problem 10.7. What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Extreme SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Extreme SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperClique-Decompositions, the new SuperHyperClasses and

SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperClique-Decompositions and the Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperClique-Decompositions” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Extreme SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperClique-Decompositions	
3. Extreme SuperHyperClique-Decompositions	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

(6), benefits and avenues for this research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Extreme SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperDuality). 1824

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a 1825
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 1826

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1827
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1828
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1829
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1830
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1831
 SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1832
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1833
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1834
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, 1835
 Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme 1836
 rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph 1837
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1838
 SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 1839
 consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such 1840
 that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1841
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1842
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1843
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1844
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1845
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1846
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1847
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme 1848
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1849
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1850
 Extreme coefficient; 1851
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1852
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1853
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a 1854
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1855
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1856
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1857
 a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme 1858
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1859
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1860
 Extreme coefficient; 1861
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1862
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1863
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1864
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1865
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1866
 SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1867
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1868
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1869
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1870
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1871
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a 1872

Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every

given Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1914

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1915
1916

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1917
1918

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1919
1920

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1921
1922

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1923
1924

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1925
1926

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1927
1928

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1929
1930

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1931
1932

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1933
1934

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i \neq 5, 7, 8}^{i=4}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1935
1936

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1937
1938

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1939
1940

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1941
1942

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1943
1944

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1945
1946

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1947
1948

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1949
1950

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1951
1952

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1953
1954

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 1955
1956

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 1957
1958

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1959

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ & z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied.
 There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
 SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
 minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 2006

Example 12.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
 The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme
 result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2013

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
&= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
& \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
&= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2026

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2027
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □ 2028

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2029
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 2030
 SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 2031
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 2032
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 2033

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 2034
 Then, 2035

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2036

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 2037
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2038

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, &V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, &\{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 2039
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 2040
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi 2041
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. 2042
 The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality 2043
 excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □ 2044

Example 12.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 2045
 SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 2046
 Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 2047
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 2048
 the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 2049

13 Extreme SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial
 contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum
 Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient; 2096-2105
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2106-2112
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
 consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
 that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2113-2119
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient; 2120-2129
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial
 contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum
 Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient. 2130-2139

Example 13.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
 in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 2140-2141

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1
 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme 2142-2144

SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
 Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
 only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a
 Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every
 given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2164
2165

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{3i+24^3_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^7_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2166
2167

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2168
2169

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2170
2171

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2172
2173

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2174
2175

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2176
2177

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{\substack{i \neq 5,7,8 \\ i=4}}^{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2178
2179

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2180
2181

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2182
2183

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2184
2185

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2186
2187

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2188
2189

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2190
2191

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2192
2193

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2194
2195

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2196
2197

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2198
2199

Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. 2200

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{E_i\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)} |_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
Then

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2212

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{E_i\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \cdot \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)} |_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL} \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}|z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ & z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme

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SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme

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SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$,

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in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 & = \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}.
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

14 Extreme SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph

- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2319-2322
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2323-2329
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2330-2339
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2340-2349
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2350-2357
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2358-2364
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 2365-2367

Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme

SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2404

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2405 2406

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2407 2408

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2409 2410

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2411 2412

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2413 2414

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2415
2416

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2417
2418

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2419
2420

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2421
2422

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2423
2424

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2425
2426

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2427
2428

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2429
2430

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2431
2432

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2433
2434

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2435
2436

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2437
2438

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2439
2440

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2441
2442

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2443
2444

Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 2445
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2447

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2448
2449

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2450
2451
2452 $\square$

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect. 2453
2454
2455

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2456
2457

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\
&= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
&= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\
&= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
&= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2458

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
\dots, \\
E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2459
2460

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} &\subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2461
2462
2463 $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect. 2464
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2466

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 2467
2468

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
&= |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} | z. \\
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (OTHERWISE). \\ &\{\}, \\ &If\ \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ &\quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &where\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (OTHERWISE)0. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 14.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)_{z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

2511

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

2512

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

2513

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

2514

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

2516

Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme

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SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme

2519

SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$,

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in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

2524

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel

2525

$ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

2526

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is

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corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is

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straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi

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isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The

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unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt

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from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Extreme SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
 consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
 that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

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of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2651
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2653
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1_{i=0}^9}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1_{i=0}^9}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2655
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2657
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2659
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1_{i=0}^9}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1_{i=0}^9}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2661
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2663
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2665
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2667
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2669
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2671
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2673
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2675
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2677
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2679
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2681
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2683
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2685
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2687
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Proposition 15.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2689
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2691

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
\dots
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2692
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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. 2694
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Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal. 2697
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Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2700
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\
& z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
 \dots, \\
 \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1} V^{EXTERNAL}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i(i-1)| E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1) \\
 &z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
& \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z \min_{|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
&= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\
&= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
 & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2758

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2759
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2760

Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2761
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 2762
 SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 2763
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 2764
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2765

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 2766
 Then, 2767

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2768

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 2769
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2770

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 2771
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is 2772
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi 2773
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The 2774
 unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt 2775
 from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 2776

Example 15.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 2777
 SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 2778
 Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 2779
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 2780
 the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2781

16 Extreme SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected.

Definition 16.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme

SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;

(iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;

(v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme
 e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme
 cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the
 Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

(vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme
 e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme
 cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of
 high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's
 either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected,
 Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient.

Example 16.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
 in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2877
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2886
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2894
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2897
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 2900
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^9, V_{22}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2933
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2936
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2939
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2942
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2945
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2948
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z.$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2951
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2954
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Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2956
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} =$$

$$= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} =$$

$$= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}$$

Proof. Let 2958

$P :$

$V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2,$

$V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3,$

$\dots,$

$E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}.$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2959
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$$V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \underset{z}{\min} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z_{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}|z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [76]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [90]** by Henry

Garrett (2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The
Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching
Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [91]** by Henry
Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the
Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By
SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [92]** by Henry
Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of
Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s
Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [93]** by Henry Garrett
(2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition
Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in
Ref. [96] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every
Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and
(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in
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there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic
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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are
proposed as book in **Ref. [121]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google
Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic
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Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different
types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic
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Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are
proposed as book in **Ref. [122]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google
Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality”
and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell
Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different
types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of
duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This
research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set,

simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1,2]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4-44,46-120]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [121,122].

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